

THE MODEL OF DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract: This article discusses the model of development of professional competence of future teachers of physical culture.

Keywords: Physical education, teacher, professional skills, theory, development, formation, knowledge.

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Prospects of further improvement of training of physical culture specialists in terms of formation of their professional competence are related to society's need for a generation that is healthy, able to work, psychologically and emotionally stable, physically developed, and has the necessary knowledge. The level of competence and special knowledge that can consciously and creatively use one's mental and motor potential. Objective realities made it necessary to reconsider the functional purpose of physical culture in the formation of a person, his worldview, and the development of adaptive abilities. This, in turn, led not only to changes in the content of education aimed at solving new educational problems, but also to a revision of the concept reflecting the essence and new content of education in the field of physical culture. We are talking about the fact that education in the field of physical education remains only education in the process of performing physical exercises, becoming an element of the culture of modern society.

In the modern world, the role of physical culture as a factor of human and society improvement is increasing noticeably. A healthy lifestyle, physical education and sports social "events" are changing into a unifying force and a national idea which serve the development of a strong state and a healthy society.

According to D.S.Likhachev, human culture moves forward not by moving in space and time, but by accumulating values.

The more values we gain, the perception of cultures, our ability to change ourselves, improving our cultural selves, and developing ourselves will be more complex and acute. All this confirms the emergency importance of culture in the 21st century.

Explaining the problems of the social phenomenon of culture, scientists (M.S. Kagan, B.S. Erasov, etc.) distinguish three main components in the general concept of culture: material, spiritual and physical parts. In the Great Soviet Encyclopedia, physical culture is interpreted as a part of the general culture of society, as one of the spheres of social activity aimed at health care, the development of human physical abilities and their use in accordance with the needs of social practice.

Physical culture is a relatively independent type of social culture. So that, it performs both general and private social functions. The general functions of physical culture are as follows: developmental, educative, educational, health and hygienic, general cultural, stimulating, controlling and inhibiting functions.

According to A.M. Maksimenko, physical culture is a type of culture that is optimal motor activity built on the basis of material and spiritual values, specially created in society for the physical development of a person. In the system of knowledge about physical culture, the central and largest category (main concept) is, of course, the concept of "physical culture"

To define this concept, it should be remembered that culture is divided according to whether it is aimed at changing the "external" (relative to man) nature or whether it is aimed at "changing" the person himself regarding optimizing his condition and development. The last part of culture can be conventionally called human culture (the convention here is that all culture is related to man, but it is not the same in different parts). Physical culture precisely belongs to this part of culture. The specific functions of physical culture according to the general signs of demonstration include:

- physical preparation of people for the intensive rhythm of life;
- general cultural development and strengthening of the body of all people, regardless of age, gender, health, level of physical development;
- satisfying people's personal needs for active motor activity and rational use of free time;
- disclosure of internal functional reserves of the body

The functions of physical culture reflect its main purpose as a type of culture. Understanding the essence of these functions allows to correctly determine the role and importance of physical culture in the life of society and to form its purpose, system of tasks, content, principles and methods of its use.

In the general social sense, physical culture is a broad field of creative activity, as well as the results of this activity in forming people's physical readiness for life, strengthening their health, developing physical abilities and movement abilities. From a personal point of view, physical culture is the way and measure of all-round physical development of a person. Taking these ideas into account, physical culture is a complex unique process and result of human activity, a means and a method of physically improving people to fulfill their social duties.

For a complete description of physical culture, it should be considered as an activity (culture as ways of activity), subject-value (culture as a sum of material and spiritual values) and result (culture as its embodiment).

Predictive model of training of a perfect physical education teacher.

The change of educational paradigms at the beginning of the century (transition from a reproductive-pedagogical civilization to a creative-pedagogical civilization) connects the goals of education with the change in the quality of a person, which should include in the near future. And it will be the ideal, self-creator of the true unity of his mental and physical powers. This applies equally to general education and vocational education. The content of training any profession, including a physical culture teacher, is primarily determined by the objective requirements of the society for the teacher.

-taking into account the specific characteristics of the taught subject, readiness to train and educate students;

- readiness to use different teaching styles, methods and tools;

- readiness for socialization, formation of general and physical culture of the person, conscious choice of vocational training programs and further development;

- readiness of students to ensure the level of training that meets the requirements of the State Education Standard;

- students' understanding the importance of respecting the rights and freedoms which are stipulated in various state and international laws and agreements;

- readiness to systematically improve one's professional qualifications, to participate in methodological work;

- desire to communicate with parents;

- readiness to comply with labor protection and safety requirements;

- readiness to ensure the protection of life and health of students during the educational process.

One of the main qualification requirements in the training of physical education specialists is the requirements for knowledge and skills on the basis of information technology provision of education, science and technology; didactic patterns in physical education and sports; methods of organizing and conducting scientific research works; to train people of different categories in movement and to have the technology to develop physical qualities in the process of physical education and sports training.

The purpose of physical education (that is, the activity of a physical education teacher) is to optimize the physical development of a person, to comprehensively improve the physical qualities characteristic of each and related abilities, together with spiritual and moral education. Qualities that characterize a socially active person and ensure the readiness of each member of society for effective work and

other activities, and accordingly, solving health care and educational tasks determine the main functions of a teacher.

Compared to teachers of other specialties, a physical education teacher works in certain conditions - conditions related to psychological stress, physical activity conditions, and external environmental factors. A physical education teacher is, in his own way, a "movement teacher". The professional specificity of the work of a physical culture teacher is that in the course of his educational and pedagogical activities, along with general pedagogical skills, movement skills are developed and improved (L.F. Spirin, in "Movement skills").

Therefore, pedagogical interaction in the form of a tool is the main educational tool of the psychological-pedagogical structure of the activity of a physical culture teacher, and its components should be considered as a dynamic, motor-constructive, tool. - organizational, motor-communicative, motor-gnostic.

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